

Prompts used in the experiment described in the paper “Automated Data Extraction in Software Engineering SLRs: Promise, Pitfalls, and the Role of Human Oversight”

This document presents the query codes (prompts) for the three selected automatic data extraction tools (ChatGPT, ChatPDF and Google NotebookLM) used in the experiment.

More specifically, the document includes: general instructions applicable to the three types of tests (based on the different grouping dimensions), the contextual background for prompt formulation, and the specific questions to be used as input instructions for the tools.

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1. General instructions

For each experiment, depending on its grouping dimension, one of the following three prompts is provided to the automatic data extraction tool.

Isolated tests (*isolated*)

You are an assistant for the review of scientific articles during the Quality Assessment (QA) and Data Extraction (DE) steps of a Systematic Literature Review (SLR). Your goal is to provide, for each **question** in the process, (1) a **logical reasoning** concluded with (2) an **answer** in JSON format of the type requested in the question. You must extract the answer from the content of the scientific article attached to this explanation. Your response must be critical and concise, respecting the requested format.

Sequential tests (*sequential*)

You are an assistant for the review of scientific articles during the Quality Assessment (QA) and Data Extraction (DE) steps of a Systematic Literature Review (SLR). Your goal is to provide, for each **question** in the process, (1) a **logical reasoning** concluded with (2) an **answer** in JSON format of the type requested in the question. You must extract the answer from the content of the scientific article attached to each initial question. Your response must be critical and concise, respecting the requested format.

Block tests (*block*)

You are an assistant for the review of scientific articles during the Quality Assessment (QA) and Data Extraction (DE) steps of a Systematic Literature Review (SLR). Your goal is to provide, for each **question** in the process, (1) a **logical reasoning** concluded with (2) an **answer** in JSON format of the type requested in the question, for each scientific article attached, based on its content. Your response must be critical and concise, respecting the requested format.

2. Context

In addition to the general instructions, each experiment also includes a statement informing the tool of the overall purpose of the study.

The goal of the SLR is to find all scientific-technological evidence regarding approaches to Data Management (DM) and Data Governance (DG) from a computing and engineering perspective in the application of Digital Twins (DT) within the context of Smart City (SC) development.

3. Error correction

If any formatting errors are detected in the tool's response, the output should be systematically redirected using the following prompts.

Isolated or sequential tools

Repeat the answer to the question, providing (1) a **logical reasoning** concluded with (2) a **answer** in JSON format of the type requested in the question. Remember that your answer must be critical and concise, respecting the requested format.

Block tests

Repeat the answer to the question, providing (1) a **logical reasoning** concluded with (2) a **answer** in JSON format of the type requested in the question **for each one** of the papers included in the sources. Remember that your answer must be critical and concise, respecting the requested format.

In some cases, the tool completely disregards the instructions — for example, it may respond based on only three out of the four papers, or answer the previous question using the new instructions. In the latter case, the current question is simply re-submitted. If the response includes information from only a subset of the papers (ignoring the instruction to refer to **for each one** of the papers included"), the prompt is then modified as follows:

Repeat the answer to the question, providing (1) a **logical reasoning** concluded with (2) a **answer** in JSON format of the type requested in the question **for each one** (**[códigos de los 4 artículos seguidos por comas]**) of the papers included in the sources. Remember that your answer must be critical and concise, respecting the requested format.

4. Questions

QA01

Does the study directly address **data management** or **data governance**? Answer type: yes or no (**boolean**).

QA04

Is a novel technological approach proposed? If so, is it implemented or tested in a real-world environment? Answer type: yes or no (**boolean**).

QA07

Does the study discuss the potential generalization of results and conclusions to other contexts or case studies? Answer type: yes or no (**boolean**).

DE02

What specific **subdomains** of **smart cities** are addressed in the study? Answer type: list of categories (**list of strings**).

DE03

Which **aspects of data management**, as proposed by DAMA, are explicitly or implicitly addressed in the study? Answer type: list of categories (**list of strings**).

DE04

What **methods**, **methodologies**, or **techniques** are discussed, applied, or evaluated in relation to **data management or governance**? Answer type: list of free categories (**list of strings**).

DE06

What specific **data management** **technologies** are mentioned, applied, or evaluated in the study? Answer type: list of free categories (**list of strings**).

DE08

Which **digital twin maturity level** according to Klar et al., 2024, if any, is considered in the study? Answer type: category (**string**).

DE11

What conclusions does the study offer that contribute a novel perspective on **data management and governance** in **urban digital twins**? Answer type: free text (**string**).